

THE UNITY OF LINGUISTICS AND THE PLACE OF STRUCTURAL LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: Modern structural linguistics, of course, does not pretend to be an exhaustive solution to this problem, but it indicates the area where the language of mathematics can be used as such a “koyne” (the area of linguistic modeling outlined in chapter I) and shows ways to expand this areas and adaptations of the language used in it for the needs all linguistics, and most importantly sharing this language with the usual language of linguistic descriptions.

Key words: structural linguistics, approach, semiotic, abstraction, humanitarian disciplines
The position of structural linguistics among humanitarian disciplines becomes clear. She is determined before all with its semiotic approach, applicable to a wide range of humanitarian disciplines. However, this is not yet determined by the wearing of structural linguistics to other linguistic disciplines. What is the place of structural linguistics in general the building of linguistics as a single science? This question is all the more it is important that some authors generally derive all mathematical linguistics (and with it a very significant part structural linguistics) beyond the language of cognition, at that time as in other circles, mainly young scientists,

The conviction is that mathematical linguistics in general designed to replace traditional linguistics (a position that, unfortunately, he took ten years ago and the author). Attempts to contrast the “traditional” and the “structural” linguistics as two different sciences have been done repeatedly. These contrasts are mainly in the following direction:

- a) opposition to the object of study;
- b) against implementation for the purpose of the study;
- c) opposition to the previous linguistic tradition;
- d) about comparison according to the research method.

As for the object of study, it is one and the same: it is a natural language and everything connected with it. May object (and such objections were repeatedly made to the author) that the object science is created by the point of view on it, and since structural linguistics studies structure, while traditional linguistics studies facts, then the objects of these sciences are different. According to the author, everything is here matter in the levels of abstraction, and traditional linguistics with this point of view does not at all represent something single.

We must not forget that already appeared in ancient grammars a clear paradigm system for declination and conjugation the main part of any grammatical description. Meanwhile only the habit of these paradigms is obscured by the fact that here we are dealing with deep structural models, degree abstraction which is very high.

The contrast for the purpose of the study is that structural linguistics as a theory of abstract models is opposed to traditional linguistics as linguistics classification, or “taxonomic”. Such a contrast, as we have already said, when discussing the polemic of descriptivist and generativist, also has a relative, and partly both the terminological nature and modern structural linguistics removes this opposition. However, our concept consists in the fact that both of these aspects are integral parts modern structural linguistics.

The definition of modern structural linguistics can be meaningfully revealed - after the explanations made in the previous paragraphs - as follows: structural linguistics is understood as a direction, consciously striving for a clear identification of semiotic aspects of the sign (in abstraction from its material embodiment), his relationship to other signs in the system and in speech, i.e., structure languages, and in this regard, the application of ideas and modeling methods. But modern structural linguistics does not come down to modeling; in it, on the contrary, there is a clear understanding that the task of a structural linguist is ultimately to describe a specific linguistic reality, that is, that material, which is prepared by traditional fields of science about the language; models are only one of the auxiliary intermediate funds. This unambiguously resolves the issue on the relationship of structural linguistics to the scientific tradition.

Some proponents of structural linguistics and especially many of her opponents emphasize the fact that structural linguistics completely breaks with the previous linguistic tradition. Perhaps historically the way it was, although, as stated in 0.2, already at the first conference on machine in 1958, a warning was voiced against a break in structural and traditional linguistics. At present time is already quite clear that the division of linguistics into two sciences: structural linguistics (field of modeling) and traditional (the area of accumulation of material) is harmful to both areas.

First of all, such a division threatens to isolate the old branches of linguistics and slow down the penetration of these branches of new ideas and methods in which more and more strongly there is a need for traditional industries such as grammar of individual languages, dialectology, translation theory and language contacts, the theory of lexicography, poetics and theory poetic speech and others. At the same time, these branches of linguistics have a stable internal content and they have a rich supply of material, the processing of which within the framework of a purely traditional methods can take many generations of linguists. There remains a huge number of described languages and dialects, for which good dictionaries and grammars have not yet been created, written at least in a good young-grammatical tradition.

Importance new exact methods proposed by structural linguistics, based on the following considerations. To the extent that linguistics deals with specific examples from specific languages, understanding between practical linguists and individual linguistic schools achieved primarily on the basis of the given examples, clear to all linguists. This period of the development of linguistics could be (of course, conditionally) likened to that period development of mathematics (for example, Indian), when the proof was replaced by a drawing and the words "look!". We hope, that there will be no offense and the analogy with the method of communication to Laputian Swift - a method consisting in the fact that the pronunciation of words replaced by an indication of specific items.

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